

COVID-19 Vaccination in Patients with Autoimmune Diseases: A Systematic Review

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic remains, even today, a global threat on both social and health levels. It is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and vaccines, antiviral drugs, and monoclonal antibodies have been approved to combat the disease. The pathogenesis of COVID-19 has various characteristics and affects multiple systems in the human body. For this reason, vaccination against COVID-19 is essential for patients with autoimmune diseases, as the immunosuppressive therapy they receive weakens the immune system to prevent it from attacking the body's own tissues and cells. Based on published literature, this systematic review attempts to answer the biological question of whether these patients should receive the COVID-19 vaccine. Three studies were selected for inclusion in this systematic review, involving patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases, autoimmune myopathies, and Sjögren's syndrome. All patients who participated in these specific studies received the CoronaVac vaccine.

Keywords: COVID-19, vaccination, autoimmune diseases, CoronaVac, systematic review, immunogenicity, safety, SARS-CoV-2, neutralizing antibodies, immunosuppression

1. Introduction

1.1 COVID-19 Disease

The COVID-19 pandemic remains, even today, a global threat on both social and health levels (Velikova and Georgiev, 2021). It is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which was first reported in December 2019 in Wuhan city, Hubei province, China (Hu *et al.*, 2021). It is known that ten vaccines have been approved for the treatment of the disease (Graña *et al.*, 2022), as well as antiviral drugs and monoclonal antibodies targeting the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Stasi *et al.*, 2020).

1.2 Pathogenesis of COVID-19

The pathogenesis of COVID-19 can be divided into three clinical stages. **Stage 1:** Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is transmitted primarily via respiratory droplets and potentially through indirect contact routes (Da Silva *et al.*, 2022). The virus subsequently attaches to epithelial cells of the nasal cavity and begins to replicate (Mason,

2020). The respiratory tract is characterized by high expression of the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), which serves as the principal receptor for SARS-CoV-2 entry. At this stage, viral spread remains localized, and the innate immune response appears limited. The viral load is relatively low; however, the patient is considered infectious (Mason, 2020).

Stage 2: The virus propagates along the respiratory tract through the conducting airways, leading to the activation of a more robust innate immune response. At this stage, COVID-19 becomes clinically manifest. It has been demonstrated that levels of the chemokine CXCL10 may steadily increase for up to one week following symptom onset (Mason, 2020). Other chemokines expressed during this phase include IP-10, CCL2/MCP-1, CXCL1, and CXCL5 (Shah et al., 2020). Approximately 80% of patients develop mild disease, with infection primarily confined to the upper respiratory tract (Mason, 2020).

Stage 3: Approximately 20% of patients with COVID-19 develop severe complications. At this stage, the viral load is significantly elevated, and a hyperinflammatory response, commonly referred to as a “cytokine storm,” is observed. Additionally, apoptosis of alveolar epithelial cells occurs, leading to the development of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) (Mason, 2020).

Regarding the pathology of COVID-19, the disease can cause dysfunction across multiple organ systems (Da Silva et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the most common pathological manifestation is pneumonia, which may be accompanied by ARDS (Shun Iida, Takeshi Arashiro, and Tadaki Suzuki, 2021). The primary receptor for SARS-CoV-2 is ACE2, which exhibits high expression levels within the respiratory system (Da Silva et al., 2022). COVID-19-associated pneumonia is characterized by diffuse alveolar damage (DAD), which histopathologically corresponds to ARDS (Shun Iida et al., 2021). The virus does not infect all alveoli simultaneously; rather, it spreads progressively, leading to extensive pulmonary damage and, ultimately, respiratory failure (Shun Iida et al., 2021).

Common manifestations of COVID-19 also include olfactory and gustatory dysfunction. There are currently insufficient data to fully elucidate the pathogenesis of these disturbances; however, ACE2 appears to play a significant role, possibly including involvement in neural tissues (Vaira et al., 2020). More specifically, ACE2 is expressed in the epithelial cells of the mucosal membranes (Vaira et al., 2020). Nevertheless, these sensory disturbances may also be associated with impairment of olfactory function (Vaira et al., 2020). Interestingly, the

proportion of patients presenting with taste disorders appears to be higher than that of patients with olfactory dysfunction, suggesting that the two conditions may not be directly correlated (Vaira et al., 2020). Finally, olfactory impairment is more likely related to ACE2 expression in the nasal mucosa rather than to virus-induced apoptosis of olfactory neurons (Vaira et al., 2020).

1.3 Immunology of COVID-19

It is well established that once the virus enters the host cell, the immune system is activated, with innate immune cells acting as the first line of defense (Merad et al., 2022). Viral recognition is mediated through Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs) (Merad et al., 2022). Specifically, Toll-like receptors (TLR3, TLR7, and TLR8) recognize viral genetic material, leading to increased production of type I interferons (IFN-I) and type III interferons (IFN- λ) (Merad et al., 2022).

In patients with either reduced or increased risk of developing severe disease, differential expression of type III interferons and interferon-stimulated genes (ISGs) has been observed (Merad et al., 2022). Cells of the innate immune system that are primarily involved in the early antiviral response include antigen-presenting cells, such as dendritic cells and macrophages.

During progression to severe COVID-19, a reduction in both the number and functionality of natural killer (NK) cells in peripheral blood has been reported (Merad et al., 2022). Additionally, a decrease in alveolar macrophages in the lungs of severely affected patients has been observed. The excessive production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, commonly referred to as a “cytokine storm,” is associated with the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) (Diao et al., 2020).

Subsequently, adaptive immunity is activated, leading to the production of virus-specific antibodies. The induction of B and T lymphocytes against the virus is crucial for long-term protection. Following viral clearance by CD8⁺ cytotoxic T cells, most of these cells undergo apoptosis (Merad et al., 2022). Upon reinfection, memory CD4⁺ T cells are activated and subsequently stimulate B lymphocytes to produce antibodies more rapidly (Merad et al., 2022). A reduction in CD8⁺ T cells has also been observed during the course of acute infection (Merad et al., 2022).

1.4 Categories of COVID-19 Vaccines

Due to the global health crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the development of effective and accessible vaccines became imperative. COVID-19 vaccines are broadly classified into four main categories (Ndwandwe and Wiysonge, 2021):

Nucleic Acid (mRNA) Vaccines (BNT162b2, mRNA-1273, CVnCoV):

These vaccines utilize messenger RNA (mRNA) technology. They contain modified mRNA in which uracil residues are replaced with 1-methylpseudouridine (m¹Ψ), enhancing molecular stability and reducing intrinsic immunogenicity. The mRNA sequence is GC-enriched and encapsulated within lipid nanoparticles, which serve as delivery vehicles (Ndwandwe and Wiysonge, 2021).

Viral Vector Vaccines (ChAdOx1, Ad26.COV2.S, Gam-COVID-Vac):

These vaccines employ a modified, replication-deficient viral vector encoding a stabilized version of the SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein, without causing disease (Ndwandwe and Wiysonge, 2021).

Protein Subunit Vaccines (NVX-CoV2373, FINLAY-FR-2):

These vaccines contain selected viral protein fragments, primarily derived from the spike protein, chosen for their ability to elicit a strong immune response. They offer a favorable safety profile, as they do not contain live virus and cannot cause infection (Ndwandwe and Wiysonge, 2021).

Whole-Virus Vaccines (Inactivated or Live-Attenuated) (CoronaVac, WIBP-CorV, BBIBP-CorV, BBV152):

Live-attenuated vaccines contain a weakened form of the virus capable of limited replication without causing disease. In contrast, inactivated vaccines contain virus particles whose genetic material has been destroyed through heat, chemical treatment, or radiation, preventing replication while still inducing an immune response (Ndwandwe and Wiysonge, 2021).

1.5 Vulnerable Groups and WHO Guidelines

Vulnerable populations include individuals with chronic diseases, autoimmune or respiratory disorders, malignancies, obesity, a history of smoking, and pregnant or postpartum women (Kompaniyets et al., 2021).

The primary entry receptor for SARS-CoV-2 is angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2). High expression levels of ACE2 are observed in the kidneys, heart, and small intestine, while lower expression levels are found in the lungs, liver, colon, and nasopharynx (Da Silva et al., 2022). This tissue distribution explains the viral tropism and the wide spectrum of pulmonary and extrapulmonary manifestations associated with COVID-19.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), primary vaccination is recommended for all eligible individuals, while booster doses are particularly advised for high-risk groups to ensure adequate and sustained protection.

1.6 Mechanisms of vaccine-induced autoimmunity

Autoimmune diseases constitute a group of disorders characterized by inflammatory immune responses directed against self-antigens (Wang, Wang and Gershwin, 2015). Infections may trigger autoimmune mechanisms through modification of self-antigens or via molecular mimicry, whereby structural similarities between microbial antigens and host antigens lead to cross-reactive immune responses (Rojas et al., 2018). The development of autoimmune diseases following vaccination is considered rare (Agmon-Levin et al., 2009). Such cases are more likely to occur in genetically predisposed individuals or in those with an already activated immune system. Vaccine adjuvants may theoretically contribute to autoimmune activation, although the precise mechanisms remain incompletely understood (Agmon-Levin et al., 2009).

1.7 Side Effects of Other Vaccines in Patients with Autoimmune Diseases

Patients with autoimmune diseases have at least a twofold increased risk of infections compared to healthy individuals, largely due to immunosuppressive or immunomodulatory therapies (Glück and Müller-Ladner, 2008). Although case reports have described disease exacerbation following vaccination, controlled studies in patients with autoimmune diseases have not demonstrated a significant increase in flare rates. However, these findings may be limited by small sample sizes (Glück and Müller-Ladner, 2008).

1.8 Aim

The purpose of this study is the systematic review of all published scientific data concerning vaccination against the SARS-CoV-2 virus in patients with autoimmune diseases. The review aims to answer the biological question of whether vaccines for SARS-CoV-2 are effective and safe for this specific vulnerable group.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Search Strategy

In this systematic review, a comprehensive literature search was performed using the PubMed and Cochrane Library databases. The search strategy incorporated the following terms: “vaccine safety,” “COVID-19,” “autoimmune diseases,” and “patients,” combined with “autoimmune diseases.”

Furthermore, the titles, abstracts, full-text articles, and reference lists of the identified studies were systematically screened to assess their relevance to the research question. The final literature search was conducted in May 2023.

Figure 2.1: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram illustrating the process of study identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion in the present systematic review.

2.2 Study Selection Criteria

Studies considered for inclusion in this systematic review and potential meta-analysis were published in 2021. Only controlled clinical trials were eligible for inclusion, following searches conducted in two electronic databases.

From the 586 initially identified records, 3 studies were ultimately selected after removal by automation tools and application of the predefined eligibility criteria.

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

1. Studies involving patients with autoimmune diseases.
2. Studies evaluating any COVID-19 vaccine.

3. Studies assessing vaccine safety in this patient population.
4. Studies published in internationally recognized peer-reviewed scientific journals.
5. Studies that were not meta-analyses, systematic reviews, or narrative reviews.
6. Studies reporting data on vaccine effectiveness.

No restrictions were applied regarding language of publication or study sample size.

The study identification and selection process is summarized in Figure 1 according to the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram.

2.3 Data Extraction

Data extracted from each included study comprised the following variables:

- **Vaccine effectiveness:** Proportion (%) of patients who developed IgG antibodies and neutralizing antibodies (NAbs).
- **Factors influencing vaccine effectiveness:** Patient pharmacological treatment, age, and sex.
- **Vaccine safety:** Proportion of patients reporting adverse events following vaccination.
- **Additional study characteristics:** Year of publication, type of autoimmune disease, type of vaccine administered, number of vaccine doses, total number of patients and control participants, and country of the studied population.

2.4 Outcomes Assessed

The analysis focused on evaluating the potential risk associated with COVID-19 vaccination in patients with autoimmune diseases, as well as assessing vaccine effectiveness within this population.

3. Results

3.1 Study Characteristics

The included studies (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021; Shinjo et al., 2022; Pasoto et al., 2022) described cases of patients who developed one or more adverse events following the first and/or second dose of the CoronaVac vaccine administered for the prevention of COVID-19. In addition, vaccine immunogenicity was evaluated after each dose in both patients and control groups.

All three studies were phase IV controlled clinical trials and included patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases, autoimmune myopathies, and Sjögren’s syndrome.

These studies were selected because they fulfilled the predefined eligibility criteria. Specifically, all three were clinical studies involving patients with autoimmune diseases and assessed both the immunogenicity and safety of the vaccine in this population. Furthermore, potential factors influencing vaccine effectiveness were evaluated. The study selection process is summarized in Figure 1.1 using the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram. The main characteristics of the included studies are summarized in Table 1.1.

Study	Country / Population	Study Duration	Patients Receiving 1st Dose (n)	Patients Receiving 2nd Dose (n)	Autoimmune Disease	Vaccine
Medeiros-Ribeiro, A.C. et al., 2021	Brazil	80 days	909	893	Autoimmune rheumatic diseases	Sinovac-CoronaVac
Shinjo, S.K. et al., 2022	Brazil	69 days	53	50	Autoimmune myopathies	Sinovac-CoronaVac
Pasoto, S.G. et al., 2022	Not reported	69 days	51	51	Sjögren’s syndrome	Sinovac-CoronaVac

Table 2.1. Summary of the studies included in the present systematic review and meta-analysis evaluating adverse events following primary COVID-19 vaccination in patients with autoimmune diseases.

3.2 Study 1

Study 1 (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021) evaluated patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases who received the CoronaVac vaccine. The study included a broad population of individuals diagnosed with autoimmune rheumatic disorders.

To assess vaccine effectiveness, anti-SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein IgG antibodies and neutralizing antibodies (NAbs) were measured. The results demonstrated a marked increase in

IgG antibody titers by day 69, corresponding to the period following administration of the second vaccine dose, both in patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases (Figure 3.1) and in healthy controls (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.1. IgG antibody titers in patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases. A substantial increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.2. IgG antibody titers in the control group. A substantial increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Regarding neutralizing antibodies, a similar pattern was observed. The proportion of patients developing positive NAb responses increased by day 69 (after the second vaccine dose) in both patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases (Figure 3.3) and healthy controls (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.3. Proportion of patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases who developed positive neutralizing antibodies. An increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.4. Proportion of control participants who developed positive neutralizing antibodies. An increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Several factors were identified as negatively influencing the production of IgG and neutralizing antibodies (NAbs) in patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases. These included age, sex, and ongoing pharmacological treatment, with pharmacological therapy demonstrating the strongest association with reduced antibody responses (Figure 3.5), followed by sex-related differences (Figure 3.6).

Specifically, 29.5% of patients did not develop detectable IgG antibodies, while 43.6% failed to develop neutralizing antibodies.

Figure 3.5. Factors negatively associated with IgG antibody production. Overall, 29.5% of patients did not develop detectable IgG antibodies.

Figure 3.6. Factors negatively associated with neutralizing antibody production. Overall, 43.6% of patients did not develop detectable NAb responses.

Regarding vaccine safety, 50.5% of patients reported adverse events following vaccination. Notably, the frequency of adverse events decreased by more than 10% after the second vaccine dose (Figure 3.7).

Patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases experienced adverse events more frequently compared to the control group. The most commonly reported adverse events included pain at the injection site, headache, somnolence, arthralgia, back pain, and sweating. Following the second dose, patients reported less pruritus at the injection site but increased sweating.

Figure 3.7. Proportion of patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases who reported adverse events after the first and second vaccine doses. A reduction in reported adverse events is observed following the second dose.

Approximately 50% of the patients were diagnosed with collagen-induced arthritis (49.6%), which represented the most prevalent autoimmune condition in the study population (Figure 3.8).

More than 60% of the total patient cohort (63%) were receiving immunosuppressive therapy at the time of vaccination (Figure 3.9).

The control group consisted primarily of individuals employed in hospital settings, with the majority working in hospital cleaning services (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.8. Distribution of autoimmune diseases evaluated in relation to the Sinovac-CoronaVac vaccine. Collagen-induced arthritis was the predominant condition, accounting for 49.6% of cases.

Figure 3.9. Pharmacological treatment of patients and corresponding proportions. Overall, 63% of patients were receiving immunosuppressive therapy.

Figure 3.10. Occupational background of control group participants. The majority were employed in hospital cleaning services.

3.3 Study 2

Study 2 (Shinjo et al., 2022) evaluated patients with autoimmune myopathies who received the CoronaVac vaccine. The study focused on individuals diagnosed with autoimmune inflammatory myopathies.

To assess vaccine effectiveness, anti-SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein IgG antibodies and neutralizing antibodies (NAbs) were measured. The findings demonstrated a significant increase in IgG antibody titers by day 69, corresponding to the period after administration of the second vaccine dose, both in patients with autoimmune myopathies (Figure 3.11) and in healthy controls (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.11. IgG antibody titers in patients with autoimmune myopathies. A marked increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.12. IgG antibody titers in the control group. A marked increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Similarly, neutralizing antibody responses increased by day 69 in both study groups. The proportion of patients with autoimmune myopathies who developed positive NAb responses increased following the second dose (Figure 3.13), as did the proportion of healthy control participants (Figure 3.14),

Figure 3.13. Proportion of patients with autoimmune myopathies who developed positive neutralizing antibodies. An increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.14. Proportion of control participants who developed positive neutralizing antibodies. An increase is observed at day 69 following the second vaccine dose.

Factors negatively associated with IgG and NAb antibody production included age, sex, and pharmacological treatment, with higher proportions attributed to immunosuppressive therapy (Figure 3.15) and sex (Figure 3.16). Overall, 35.1% of patients did not develop detectable IgG antibodies, and 48.6% did not develop detectable NAb.

Figure 3.15: Graph illustrating factors negatively associated with IgG antibody production. Overall, 35.1% of patients did not develop IgG antibodies.

Figure 3.16: Graph illustrating factors negatively associated with NAb production. Overall, 48.6% of patients did not develop NAb.

The proportion of patients who experienced adverse events was 49.06% after the first vaccine dose and decreased to 46% following the second dose (Figure 3.17). Adverse events were comparable between patients and the control group. After the first dose, patients with autoimmune myopathies reported a higher proportion of headache compared with controls.

Figure 3.17: Graph illustrating patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases who experienced adverse events after the first and second vaccine doses. A reduction in adverse events is observed after the second dose.

Approximately 47.20% of patients were diagnosed with antisynthetase syndrome (Figure 3.18). Overall, 83% of patients were receiving immunosuppressive therapy (Figure 3.19).

Figure 3.18: Graph illustrating the types of autoimmune diseases evaluated in relation to the Sinovac-CoronaVac vaccine. Antisynthetase syndrome accounted for the highest proportion (47.20%).

Figure 3.19: Graph illustrating the pharmacological treatment received by patients with autoimmune myopathies and the proportion of patients receiving each therapy. Overall, 83% of patients were receiving immunosuppressive treatment.

3.4 Study 3

Study 3 (Pasoto et al., 2022) included exclusively patients with Sjögren’s syndrome who received the CoronaVac vaccine. To evaluate vaccine immunogenicity, anti-SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein IgG antibodies and neutralizing antibodies (NAb) were measured.

The results demonstrated that IgG antibody titers increased at day 69, corresponding to the period following the second vaccine dose, both in patients (Figure 3.20) and in healthy controls (Figure 3.21).

Figure 3.20: Graph illustrating the percentage of IgG antibody titers in patients with Sjögren’s syndrome. An increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.21: Graph illustrating the percentage of IgG antibody titers in individuals in the control group. An increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Regarding neutralizing antibodies, NAb levels increased at day 69, following the second vaccine dose, both in patients (Figure 3.22) and in healthy controls (Figure 3.23).

Figure 3.22: Graph illustrating the percentage of patients with Sjögren's syndrome who developed positive NAb. An increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Figure 3.23: Graph illustrating the percentage of control group individuals who developed positive NAb. An increase is observed at day 69, following the second vaccine dose.

Factors negatively associated with IgG and NAb production included age, sex, and pharmacological treatment, with higher proportions attributed to immunosuppressive therapy (Figure 3.24) and sex (Figure 3.25). Overall, 32.5% of patients did not develop detectable IgG antibodies, and 47.5% did not develop detectable neutralizing antibodies.

Figure 3.24: Graph illustrating factors negatively associated with IgG antibody production. Overall, 32.5% of patients did not develop IgG antibodies.

Figure 3.25: Graph illustrating factors negatively associated with NAb production. Overall, 47.5% of patients did not develop NAb.

The proportion of patients who experienced adverse events was 49.02% after the first vaccine dose and decreased to 47.06% following the second dose (Figure 3.26). Vomiting, muscle weakness, arthralgia, and back pain were reported at higher frequencies among patients with Sjögren’s syndrome compared with controls.

Figure 3.26: Graph illustrating patients with Sjögren’s syndrome who experienced adverse events after the first and second vaccine doses. A reduction in adverse events is observed after the second dose.

Overall, 62.50% of patients were receiving hydroxychloroquine (Figure 3.27).

Figure 3.27: Graph illustrating the pharmacological treatment received by patients and the proportion of patients receiving each therapy. Overall, 62.50% of patients were receiving hydroxychloroquine.

4. Discussion

Overall, the three clinical studies (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021; Shinjo et al., 2022; Pasoto et al., 2022) converge on the conclusion that the CoronaVac vaccine appears to be safe and immunogenic in patients with autoimmune diseases.

In the first study (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021), the most prevalent autoimmune condition among participants was rheumatoid arthritis, whereas in the second study (Shinjo et al., 2022) antisynthetase syndrome predominated. The third clinical study (Pasoto et al., 2022) exclusively included patients with Sjögren's syndrome. Therefore, the overall findings of the included studies are largely driven by these specific autoimmune conditions, while data regarding other autoimmune diseases remain limited. This suggests that the available evidence for patients with less represented autoimmune disorders is insufficient.

It is noteworthy that the first study (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021), which included patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases, reported the occupational background of the control group, whereas this information was not provided in the other two studies (Pasoto et al., 2022; Shinjo et al., 2022). Specifically, control participants were hospital cleaning staff, healthcare professionals, hospital administrative employees, or their relatives. This raises concerns regarding potential asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection during the study period, which may not have been identified by either investigators or participants. Healthcare workers have been shown to have an increased risk of COVID-19 infection (Shields et al., 2020). Consequently, the reported levels of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG and neutralizing antibodies in the control group may have been influenced by unrecognized prior exposure, potentially affecting the reliability of immunogenicity comparisons.

Regarding antibody production, all three studies (Pasoto et al., 2022; Shinjo et al., 2022; Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021) consistently reported lower anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG and neutralizing antibody responses in patients compared with control groups. Moreover, the factors influencing antibody production were similar across studies. Age and sex were identified as significant determinants. Increasing age is associated with immunosenescence, leading to reduced antibody titers compared with younger individuals (Fink and Klein, 2018; Stiasny et al., 2012). Although previous evidence suggests that females, both younger and older, generally develop higher antibody titers (Fink and Klein, 2018), the included studies reported reduced anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG and neutralizing antibody responses in female patients compared with male patients.

Pharmacological treatment was also identified as a negative factor influencing antibody production. Most patients included in these studies were receiving immunosuppressive therapy for the management of their underlying autoimmune disease. These agents modulate or

suppress immune system activity to prevent immune-mediated tissue damage (Velikova and Georgiev, 2021). Therefore, reduced antibody responses in this population are biologically plausible and do not imply that vaccination should be avoided in patients receiving immunosuppressive treatment.

In terms of safety, CoronaVac appears to be well tolerated in patients with autoimmune diseases, with predominantly mild adverse events reported. Notably, the same predefined adverse events were assessed across studies, in accordance with World Health Organization guidelines. However, disease-specific outcomes, such as potential autoimmune disease flares or relapse, were not systematically evaluated, and therefore could not be adequately assessed. Across all three studies, adverse events decreased following the second vaccine dose.

In the first study (Medeiros-Ribeiro et al., 2021), patients with autoimmune rheumatic diseases reported adverse events more frequently than controls. The most common events included injection-site pain, headache, somnolence, arthralgia, back pain, and sweating. After the second dose, patients reported less injection-site pruritus but increased sweating. In the second study (Shinjo et al., 2022), adverse events were comparable between patients and controls, although patients with autoimmune myopathies reported a higher frequency of headache following the first dose. In the third study (Pasoto et al., 2022), vomiting, muscle weakness, arthralgia, and back pain were reported more frequently among patients with Sjögren's syndrome compared with controls.

In conclusion, the clinical relevance of the present work is considerable, as it highlights the importance of vaccination and provides scientific evidence addressing concerns regarding COVID-19 vaccination in patients with autoimmune diseases.

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